

Dataset on Biomass Potential for Environmental Protection to Generate Energy in Jordan from Olives and Other Biomasses and Review of Biomass Energy Conversion Technologies

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Protection, Biomass, Thermal Energy, Electricity Generation, Jordan</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5595300</p>	<p><i>Data on available biomass resources in Jordan were estimated from agriculture wastes, animal waste and municipal solid waste for environmental protection. The potential energy recovered from these residues was assessed based on mass burn scenario. The total heating value of these residues were estimated at 49 PJ, this is equivalent to 2,040 (thousand tons of oil equivalent) which represent 20% of national energy consumption of 9,750 ktoe in 2018. For electricity generation, the analysis shows a potential to generate around 2,750 GWh which is around 16% of the electrical power consumed in 2018 of 17,500 GWh. The development and use of such forms of energy help sustainable development through economic growth and pollution control.</i></p>

Introduction

Biomass is a potential source of energy that can decrease Jordan dependence on fossil fuel as the main energy source. Environmental policies today are mostly dedicated to support the development and application of renewable energy technologies as a sustainable source of energy [1-2]. In addition to solar and wind energy resources, the increase use of biomass to generate electricity and heat is one feature of this transition. Huge amounts of agricultural residues are produced globally, and most of this residue can be used for energy generation because of its high biomass content. Therefore, converting these wastes into energy will increase agriculture residues value and reduces their disposal environmental impact.

Energy is necessary for economic development, community growth and better life quality worldwide [3]. The fluctuation of oil prices put more pressure on the global economy especially third world countries. Looking for cheap sustainable alternatives clean energy sources became top priority in developed countries [4-6]. One of the available options is the conversion of biomass to thermal or electrical energy [7].

Biomass, mostly wood, has been used as a major source of renewable energy because of its availability worldwide [8]. Biomass with annual energy consumption of 14% globally becomes a major energy source besides 15% and 12% from coal [9]. Biomass amounts depend on climate conditions, production activities, geographical locations and population density.

Agricultural residues and its by product are generated in large quantities worldwide; which might be used for energy production. This will reduce the waste environmental impacts and add value to the waste materials by adopting "waste to energy principle" (WtE). This might be of additional income for farmers by adopting a more sustainable bioenergetics' system. Solid biomass can be burned directly for space heating and/or transformed into gaseous or liquid fuels; to be used later for thermal applications and electricity generation.

The dataset investigated the biomass energy potential from different resources in Jordan for potential energy production. Biomasses from olive grove pruning, olive oil mills residues, agricultural wastes, livestock wastes, and municipal solid wastes were estimated. Based on the quantity of wastes estimated produced, the energy generation potential from these residues were evaluated based on two scenarios: Mass Burning and biogas production. The results will serve as a base line for further innovative feasibility assessments on using biomass resources to support local energy consumption. Currently, most of these biomasses produced are burned in the field and some used for homes heating in winter in the countryside.

2 Energy Situations in Jordan

The nation currently relies heavily on imported oil which account for 90% in 2108 which accounted for 10% of the national GDP [10]. The demand for electricity was 20,690.20 GWh in 2018 which is expected to rise 21,940 GWh by 2020 [10]. The main energy consumption added up to 9,712 Ktoe and the renewable energy contributed roughly 7.32% mainly from solar and wind energy as shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1. Evolution of renewable energy production to the total energy balance (KTOE) [10]

The energy consumption of major sectors in 2018 are shown in Fig 2. Transportation sector consumed large fraction of final energy consumption approx. 49% [10].

Fig. 2. Primary energy consumption by sector in Jordan in 2018 (9,712 Ktoe) [10]

Due to the arid climate there is not much forestry in the country, trees pruning, and agriculture residues are burned in country sides and desert as the main source of energy for cooking and heating. Other crop residues are either mixed with soil as soil amendment or burnt in the field.

Biomass energy potential is also attractive in the form of agriculture waste, urban wastes, and livestock residues. The rapid technological advancements make waste-to-energy (WtE) principle viable.

3. Methodology

Quantities of available biomasses which might be used for energy potential were determined from various resources in Jordan. Biomasses from agricultural residues, animal wastes and municipal solid wastes were

estimated. The goal is to assess their energy recovery potential for the generation of thermal and/or electrical energy.

The biomass assessment is based on available biomass resources which includes:

1. Estimating biomass quantity produced from different agricultural and human activities in the country based on the average of five years of production (2014–2018) to minimize annual fluctuation of biomass data.
2. The total dry biomass residues produced were estimated using the residue to product ratio coefficient (RPR). The annual livestock wastes generation were based on animal numbers and their daily manure production per animal.
3. The energy availability factors reported by Hall et al., [32] were used to estimate quantity of residues that might be used in energy generation processes. The energy factors used are 25% for agricultural residues, 12.5% for animal dung (except cattle and poultry) and 75% for MSW [32]. For poultry and cattle, a factor of 90% was used since these livestock are raised in private farms, where all farm and livestock wastes are collected. These factors represent the actual residue portion that can be collected and used for energy generation from different resource. Olive groves residues are generally hard to be collected due to scatter small farming. An estimation of the production of 3 ton per hectare was assumed [32]. While olive cake (locally name Jift) is produced at olive mill and can be easily collected, so a factor of **90%** was used.
3. The potential energy recovery that might be obtained from various biomass resources was estimated based combustion of waste. The assessment might lead policymakers, stakeholders to develop industrial strategies and therefore support decision making processes to use biomass energy.

4. Biomass potential

4.1. Biomass potential

The use of biomass as feedstock in generating renewable alternatives for fossil fuels has gained the attention of researchers worldwide [11]. The energy generation potential from different biomass resources was investigated in this study.

4.2 Biomass potential from olive groves in Jordan

Olive tree plantation is a common practice in all Mediterranean region [8]. Olive plantation groves are the main agricultural plantation in Jordan and occupy around 75% of arable land (the orchards). Approximately, around 25 million olive trees, increases annually by 1 million trees [33], making it the top agricultural product in the country. The orchards are typically small, planted in hilly areas, difficult to access, and expensive to harvest by hand [34].

In 2018, more than 220,000 tons of olives were harvested, which produced 35,000 tons of oil. Additionally, around 60,000 tons of olive pomace (olive cake or locally called Jift) and around 200,000 m³ of olive mills wastewaters (OMWWs) were produced in Jordan [35-37]. Most of the olive pomace produced in the country is used after drying and pressing as a fuel source for space heating in winter as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Pressed dry pomace

The heating value of the olive tree pruning between 17.991-19.246 MJ/kg [8], taking the average of 18.5 MJ/kg and energy availability factor of 75% [32]. The energy production from olive tree pruning estimated at 2,164.5 TJ Table 4. For olive pomace the heating value 15-17 MJ/kg, the average of 16 MJ/kg was taken and energy availability factor of 90% [32] was used. The estimated energy of olive pomace is around 1,108.80 TJ. For olive mill wastewater (OMWW) the heating value 15-17 MJ/kg, the average of 14.40 MJ/kg was taken and energy availability factor of 90% [32] was also used. The estimated energy content of OMWW is around 2,592 TJ.

4.3 Energy potential from other agricultural activities

Agricultural residues are produced after harvesting of agricultural crop, which is normally consist of crop remaining that are normally of no value, such as leaves, stem, empty fruit bunches, and stalks.

4.3.1 Vegetable residues

Vegetables such as tomatoes, cucumber, pepper, potato, eggplants, onion, cabbage, cauliflower, lettuce, and watermelon are produced for local consumption and for export. The average annual vegetable production reached 1,870,000 ton. Residues quantities were estimated based on product to residue ratios (PRP) of 0.50 [32] and energy content of 6.0 MJ/kg [21]. The energy availability factor of 25% [32] was assumed due to low collection efficiency, the potential energy from vegetable residues was estimated at 280.5 TJ.

4.3.2 Pasture crops residues

Field crops are cultivated in Jordan valley and in the northwest of the country in the rainfed areas. The available annual residue was projected at 391 thousand tons [33, 38, 39]. Clover Trifol is rank first and account for 70% of the production followed by Maize, barley, and wheat of 9.5%, 9%, and 8%, respectively [33].

Residues quantities per kg of grain harvested are estimated based on product to residue ratios (PRR) of 2.0 kg [40,41] consists of leaves, straws stalks and husk. The energy content 14.65 - 18.60 MJ/kg [29], the average 16.58 MJ/kg was taken in our estimation. The energy availability factor of 25% was used as reported by [32], so the total energy from crop residues is projected at 1,620 TJ.

4.3.3 Fruit residues

Citrus, banana, grapes, apple and peach are also grown and produced in Jordan. The annual yield is estimated at 310,000 tons, the product to residue ratios (PRR) of 2 was reported for most fruits [40,42], while a value of 3 was taken for olive trees pruning [22]. The generated fruit residues are estimated at 372 thousand ton (based on the average annual fruit production of 310,000 ton/year). The average energy content for most fruit is 13.0 MJ/kg [32]. So, the fruit residues energy content is estimated at 4,836 TJ. Considering that most fruit residues have energy availability factor of 25% [32], the available energy from fruit remains is projected at 1,209 TJ. Olive residues have the greatest contribution with 75%, followed by citrus trees residues 15%, banana residues 9%, apple and grapes residues have roughly equal share of 5%.

4.3.4 Animal Wastes

Cattle husbandry includes cows, poultry, goats and sheep. In 2018 there were 3.15 million sheep, 1,17 million goats 75,000 cows, 15,000 camels 12,500 horses and donkeys, and 41.5 million poultry mainly chicken. It is estimated that the dry livestock manure is roughly 4,306 thousand ton. Sheep's and goats have large share with 70.23%. Poultry has 21.2%, while cows, camels, horses, and donkeys share around 8.57%. Animal manure heating values varies from 13.50 for chickens to 17.80 MJ/kg for sheep and goat [41].

Cattle and poultry belong to private sector which makes wastes collection and handling efficient. Therefore, energy availability factor of 90% can be assumed, in contrast, sheep and goats, have low collection efficiency, because they depend largely on grazing, therefore low energy availability factor of 12.5% was assumed for their wastes [32].

Considering the collection efficiencies and energy availability factors, the amount of waste available for energy production is around 4,306 thousand ton. The anticipated potential energy from animals' residues can reached up to 21.65 PJ. The highest contribution from poultry with 51.24%, while sheep and goats contribute 31.1%. cattle can contribute 16.84%, while camel 0.47% and the least horses and donkeys 0.38%.

4.3.5 Municipal Solid Wastes (MSW)

Municipal waste is produced daily by homes, commercial and industrial activities. The waste includes biodegradable ingredients such as food, yard waste, wood, papers and cardboards in addition to plastics, textiles, glass, and metal. The generation of this type of waste is steadily increasing in Jordan at a rate of 3.5% over the past three decades [16]. The population of Jordan reached 10.5 million [43], the generated municipal solid waste which was collected by local municipalities reached 3.2 million tons in 2018 [16]. The estimated daily generation of waste per capita in the country is estimated at 0.6 - 0.9 kg in rural and urban areas, respectively [44]. The combustible material comprises roughly 90% of the total waste (food residues 60%, papers 15%, cardboard, and 15% plastic) [16]. The potential energy from the combustible part was reported at 11.49 MJ/kg [44, 45], so the projected potential energy from MSW is estimated at 18.031 TJ.

Table 1: Biomass potential in Jordan

	ktoe/year	%
Agriculture residues	375.79	19.16
Olive grove Olive oil industry	245.57	12.52
Field crops	67.86	3.33
Fruit trees	50.62	2.48
Vegetables	11.74	0.60
Animal waste	906.48	42.34
Poultry	464.44	23.69
Sheep	205.40	10.48
Cow	152.61	7.49
Goat	76.28	3.89
Camel	4.23	0.21
Horse and Donkey	3.52	0.17
MSW	754.92	38.50
Middle	509.16	25.97
North	175.55	8.95
South	70.21	3.58
Total Biomass potential in Jordan	2,037	

The biomass potential energy in Jordan is around 2,037 ktoe annually as shown in Table 1. Of this total amount of energy, 906.48 ktoe is obtained from animal and poultry residues (44.50%), 754.92 ktoe from MSW (38.50%) and agriculture residues 375.79 ktoe (19.16%) [46]. This is equivalent to 21% of national energy consumption of 9,712 ktoe in 2018 [10]. This is equivalent to 481% of the local oil and gas production of 423.68 ktoe in 2018 [10]. For agriculture residues, roughly 65.35% is obtained from olive tree residues (246 ktoe/year), 18% from field 13.5 % from fruit trees, crops and 3.12% from vegetable (Table 1). MSW, animal and poultry waste and the olive sector can be considered as the major producer of residual biomass in Jordan

which account for 93.62% of biomass potential energy. The energy obtained from various biomass resources contributes to rural areas development, energy diversification, increases self-energy sufficiency and gives a sustainable substitute for fossil fuels. Additionally, biomass is a renewable energy source that can be used as a thermal source for heating, electricity generation, and automobile transportation, and reduces 890 g of CO₂/kWh if it is used instead of fossil fuel [33]. Biomass end use depends mostly on characteristics of raw material. Ninety percent of the biomass in Jordan used to generate thermal energy in domestic heating systems, (3%) generates electricity and (7%) used in olive oil industries due to the abundance of olive orchards and their closeness to the industry.

Table 2 shows potential electricity production by direct combustion from trees, vegetables, livestock, and MSW.

Table 2: Potential of electricity generation from biomass combustion [46]

Biomass resource	Average annual waste generated (10 ³ ton)	Energy availability factor [63]	Electricity Generation (GWh)
Trees	624	0.75	312
Vegetables and Field crops	578	0.25	115
Animal	3,993	0.125	615
Poultry	913	0.90	649
MSW (ton/day)	4,300		1050
Total			2,741

Figure 3 shows electricity generated in 2018 (17,541 GWh) and their end users

Fig. 3. Electrical power generation consumption by sector in 2018 [46]

If the entire MSW is used for energy generation, the expected total CO₂ equivalent emission saving are estimated between 3,117.5 and 6,536 thousand-ton annually. The CO₂ emissions reduction equivalents for electricity generated from MSW are calculated based on emission saving between 725-1520 kg CO₂/t of MSW [48].

6. Conclusions

It is estimated that agricultural and animal residues can produce 1,535 and 4,306 thousand ton annually, respectively. The contribution of collected MSW is add up to 1,569.50 thousand ton annually. IF the feedstocks are combusted directly to generate electricity, the projected electrical energy produced can reach 2,746 GWh. The contribution of these resources to the total electricity generation by direct combustion is 38.10% for MSW, 23.64% for poultry wastes and 8.46% for olive pomace. They represent the best feedstocks for generation of electricity either by direct combustion or biogas production.

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